

SOFT GAMMA IDEALS OF SOFT GAMMA SEMIGROUPS

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Paper Received On: 20 AUGUST 2025

Peer Reviewed On: 24 SEPTEMBER 2025

Published On: 01 OCTOBER 2025

Abstract

Soft set theory is an important mathematical tool to deal with uncertainty and has intensive applications in the field of game theory, smoothness of functions, theory of measurement etc. In the present paper We gave some characterization of uni-soft Γ -semigroup, uni-soft Γ -left and right Γ -ideal and uni-soft quasi Γ -ideal of a soft Γ -semigroup. Using the notion of uni-soft quasi- Γ -ideal we have also discussed the characterization of a regular Γ -semigroup.

Keywords: Soft set, Uni-soft gamma semigroup, Uni-soft gamma ideals, uni-soft Γ -subsemigroup, uni-soft quasi Γ -ideal.

1. Introduction:

Soft set theory is an important tool in mathematics evolved at the verge of 19th century to solve many of the problems that we are facing in practical life, specially in the fields of medical sciences, physics, engineering, and computer science. The classical set theory is not fully suitable while solving the problems that arise in above said fields as it has limited resources. Many mathematical theories have been developed in the last five decades dealing such kinds of problems. But these theories were not fully suitable to conduct such problems of uncertainties due to the inadequacy of parameterization tool. To overcome this, in 1999 Molodtsov[3] introduced the soft set theory as a new mathematical tool for dealing with uncertainties. He applied his theory into several directions such as smoothness of functions, integration, theory of probability successfully. Aslıhan Sezgina et.al [1] Introduced the basic properties of operation on soft sets such as restricted intersection, restricted union and

difference. They have extended the theoretical aspect of operations on soft sets. Chang Su Kim et.al [2] have introduced and considered some characterization of uni-soft semigroup, uni-soft left and right ideal and uni-soft quasi ideal of a soft semigroup. Using the notion of uni-soft quasi-ideal they have also discussed the characterization of a regular semigroup. By applying the soft set theory concepts Mohammad yahya Abbasi et.al [4] have characterized the ternary semigroups with involution. Seok Zun Song et.al [5] have introduced the notion of int-soft semigroups and int-soft ideals and investigated several properties.

2. Definitions and preliminaries.

Definition 2.1: Let U be an initial universe and E be a set parameters or attributes with respect to U . Then a pair (F, A) is called a soft set over U if $F: E \rightarrow P(U)$, where $P(U)$ denotes the power set of U and $A \subseteq E$. A soft set (F, A) over U is a parameterized family of subsets of U .

For two soft sets (F, M) and (G, M) we define $(F, M) \subseteq (G, M)$ if $F(x) \subseteq G(x)$ for $x \in M$.

The soft union of (F, M) and (G, M) over U is defined to be the set $(F \cup G, M)$ over U such that $(F \cup G)(x) = F(x) \cup G(x)$ for all $x \in M$. Similarly the soft intersection can defined as $(F \cap G)(x) = F(x) \cap G(x)$ for all $x \in M$.

In what follows, we take $E = M$, as set of parameters which is a Γ -semigroup unless otherwise specified.

Definition 2.2: A soft set (F, M) over U is called a uni-soft Γ -semigroup over U , if it satisfies $F(x\alpha y) \subseteq F(x) \cup F(y)$ for all $x, y \in M$ and $\alpha \in \Gamma$.

Definition 2.3: A soft set (F, M) over U is called a uni-soft left (resp. right) Γ -ideal over U if $F(x\alpha y) \subseteq F(y)$ ($F(x\alpha y) \subseteq F(x)$), for all $x, y \in M$ and $\alpha \in \Gamma$. If (F, M) is both uni-soft left Γ -ideal and uni-soft right Γ -ideal over U , we say that (F, M) is uni-soft two-sided Γ -ideal over U .

Example 2.4: Let $M = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\Gamma = \{\alpha, \beta\}$. We define $aab = a \cdot b$ for all $a, b \in M$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$ where \cdot is defined by the Cayley's table as follows,

\cdot	a	b	c	d
a	a	a	a	a
b	a	a	a	a
c	a	a	b	a
d	a	a	b	b

Let (F, M) be a soft set over U defined by,

$$F: M \rightarrow P(U), x \rightarrow \begin{cases} \eta_1 & \text{if } x = a \\ \eta_2 & \text{if } x = b \\ \eta_3 & \text{if } x = c \\ \eta_4 & \text{if } x = d \end{cases} \text{ with } \eta_1 \subseteq \eta_2 \subseteq \eta_3 \subseteq \eta_4 \text{ where } \eta_i \in P(U).$$

Clearly (F, M) is uni-soft left Γ -ideal and uni-soft right Γ -ideal over U . Suppose if (F, M) is a uni-soft left Γ -ideal, then $F(x\alpha y) \subseteq F(y) \subseteq F(x) \cup F(y)$ for any $x, y \in M$ and $\alpha \in \Gamma$. So (F, M) is uni-soft Γ -semigroup over U . Similarly, if (F, M) is a uni-soft right Γ -ideal, then $F(x\alpha y) \subseteq F(x) \subseteq F(x) \cup F(y)$, for any $x, y \in M$ and $\alpha \in \Gamma$. So (F, M) is uni-soft Γ -semigroup over U . Thus every uni-soft left /right Γ -ideal is a uni-soft Γ -semigroup over U . But the converse need not be true.

Example 2.5: Let $M = \{a, b, c, d, e, f\}$ and $\Gamma = \{\alpha, \beta\}$. We define $a\alpha b = a \cdot b$ for all $a, b \in M$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$, where \cdot is defined by the Cayley's table as follows,

\cdot	a	b	c	d	e	f
a	a	a	a	a	a	a
b	a	b	b	b	b	b
c	a	b	c	d	b	b
d	a	b	b	b	c	d
e	a	b	e	f	b	b
f	a	b	b	b	e	f

Define the soft set (F, M) over U by $F: M \rightarrow P(U), x \rightarrow \begin{cases} \eta_1 & \text{if } x = a \\ \eta_2 & \text{if } x = b \\ \eta_5 & \text{if } x = c, e \\ \eta_4 & \text{if } x = d \\ \eta_3 & \text{if } x = f \end{cases}$

Where $\eta_1, \eta_2, \eta_3, \eta_4, \eta_5 \in P(U)$ with $\eta_1 \subseteq \eta_2 \subseteq \eta_3 \subseteq \eta_4 \subseteq \eta_5$. Clearly (F, M) is a uni-soft Γ -semigroup over U . Since $F(d\alpha f) = F(d \cdot f) = F(d) = \eta_4 \not\subseteq \eta_3 = F(f)$, (F, M) is not a uni-soft left Γ -ideal over U . Similarly, let (G, M) be a soft set over U define as follows,

$$G: M \rightarrow P(U), x \rightarrow \begin{cases} \eta_1 & \text{if } x = a, b \\ \eta_3 & \text{if } x = c \\ \eta_2 & \text{if } x = d \\ \eta_4 & \text{if } x = e, f \end{cases}$$

Where $\eta_1, \eta_2, \eta_3, \eta_4 \in P(U)$ with $\eta_1 \subseteq \eta_2 \subseteq \eta_3 \subseteq \eta_4$. Then (G, M) is a uni-soft Γ -semigroup over U . Consider, $G(d\alpha e) = G(d \cdot e) = G(c) = \eta_3 \not\subseteq \eta_2 = G(d)$. Hence (G, M) is not a uni-soft right Γ -ideal over U .

For a non-empty subset A of M , the soft set (χ_A, M) , where χ_A is defined as

$$\chi_A: M \rightarrow P(U), x \rightarrow \begin{cases} U & \text{if } x \in A \\ \emptyset & \text{if } x \notin A \end{cases} \text{ is called the uni-characteristic soft set. The set } (\chi_M, M)$$

is called the uni-empty soft set over U .

Definition 2.6: Let (F, M) be any soft set over U . Then η -exclusive set of (F, M) is defined by $e_M(F: \eta) = \{x \in M / F(x) \subseteq \eta\}$ for $\eta \subseteq U$.

Definition 2.7. Let (F, M) and (G, M) be two soft sets over U . Then the uni-soft product of (F, M) and (G, M) is a soft set $(F \circ G, M)$ over U defined by,

$$(F \circ G)(x) = \begin{cases} \bigcap_{x=y\alpha z} \{F(y) \cup (z)\} & \text{if there exists } y, z \in M, \alpha \in \Gamma \text{ such that } x = y\alpha z \\ U & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Definition 2.8: Let (F, M) be a soft set over U . For a subset $\eta \in P(U)$ with $e_M(F: \eta) \neq \emptyset$, define the soft set (F^*, M) over U by,

$$F^*: M \rightarrow P(U), x \rightarrow \begin{cases} F(x) & \text{if } x \in e_M(F: \eta) \\ \rho & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \text{ where } \rho \text{ is a subset of } U \text{ with } F(x) \subseteq \rho.$$

Definition 2.9: A soft set (F, M) over U is called a uni-soft quasi Γ -ideal of M over U if, $(F, M) \subseteq (F \circ \chi_M, M) \cup (\chi_M \circ F, M)$.

3. Main Results.

Theorem 3.1: Let A be any non-empty subset of M . Then A is left(resp. right) Γ -ideal of M if and only if the uni-characteristic soft set (χ_A, M) over U is a uni-soft left(resp. right) Γ -ideal over U .

Proof: Suppose that A is a left Γ -ideal of M and let $x, y \in M, \alpha \in \Gamma$. If $y \notin A$, then $\chi_A(x\alpha y) \subseteq U = \chi_A(y)$. If $y \in A$, then $x\alpha y \in A$ for all $x \in M, \alpha \in \Gamma$ as A is a left Γ -ideal of M . So $\chi_A(x\alpha y) = \emptyset = \chi_A(y)$. Hence $\chi_A(x\alpha y) \subseteq \chi_A(y)$ in both the cases. $\therefore (\chi_A, M)$ is a uni-soft left Γ -ideal over U . Similarly, if we assume that A is a right Γ -ideal of M , we can prove that (χ_A, M) is a uni-soft right Γ -ideal over U .

Conversely, Suppose that (χ_A, M) is a uni-soft left Γ -ideal over U . Let $x \in M$, $\alpha \in \Gamma$, $y \in A$. Then $\chi_A(y) = \emptyset$. $\therefore \chi_A(x\alpha y) \subseteq \chi_A(y) = \emptyset$. So $\chi_A(x\alpha y) = \emptyset$. Which implies $x\alpha y \in A$. Hence A is a left Γ -ideal of M . Similarly if we take (χ_A, M) is a uni-soft right Γ -ideal over U , we can prove that A is a right Γ -ideal of M .

Corollary 3.2 : Let A be any non-empty subset of M . Then A is a two sided Γ -ideal of M if and only if the uni-characteristic soft set (χ_A, M) over U is a uni-soft two sided Γ -ideal over U .

Theorem 3.3 : Let (F, M) be any soft set over U . Then (F, M) is a uni-soft Γ -semigroup over U if and only if for $\eta \in P(U)$, $e_M(F: \eta)$ is a uni-soft Γ -subsemigroup of M over U with $e_M(F: \eta) \neq \emptyset$.

Proof: Assume that (F, M) is a uni-soft Γ -semigroup over U . Let $\eta \in P(U)$ with $e_M(F: \eta) \neq \emptyset$ and $x, y \in e_M(F: \eta)$, $\alpha \in \Gamma$. Then $F(x) \subseteq \eta$, $F(y) \subseteq \eta$. Since (F, M) is a uni-soft Γ -semigroup over U , $F(x\alpha y) \subseteq F(x) \cup F(y) \subseteq \eta \cup \eta = \eta$. So $x\alpha y \in e_M(F: \eta)$.

Thus $e_M(F: \eta)$ is a uni-soft Γ -subsemigroup over U .

Conversely, suppose that $\eta \in P(U)$, $e_M(F: \eta) \neq \emptyset$, $e_M(F: \eta)$ is a uni-soft Γ -subsemigroup of M over U . Let $x, y \in M$, $\alpha \in \Gamma$ such that $F(x) = \eta_1$, $F(y) = \eta_2$. Then $F(x) \subseteq \eta$, $F(y) \subseteq \eta$ when $\eta = \eta_1 \cup \eta_2$. So $x, y \in e_M(F: \eta)$. Since $e_M(F: \eta)$ is a uni-soft Γ -subsemigroup of M over U , $x\alpha y \in e_M(F: \eta)$ for $\alpha \in \Gamma$. $\therefore F(x\alpha y) \subseteq \eta = \eta_1 \cup \eta_2 = F(x) \cup F(y)$, for $\eta_1, \eta_2 \subseteq U$.

Hence (F, M) is a uni-soft Γ -semigroup over U .

Theorem 3.4 : Let (F, M) be a soft set over U . Then (F, M) is a uni-soft left (resp. right) Γ -ideal over U if and only if for $\eta \in P(U)$, $e_M(F: \eta) \neq \emptyset$, $e_M(F: \eta)$ is a uni-soft left (resp. right) Γ -ideal over U .

Proof: Proof of this theorem is same as that of theorem 6.1.9.

Corollary 3.5: Let (F, M) be a soft set over U . Then (F, M) is a uni-soft two sided Γ -ideal over U if and only if for $\eta \in P(U)$, $e_M(F: \eta) \neq \emptyset$, $e_M(F: \eta)$ is a uni-soft two sided Γ -ideal of M over U .

Proposition 3.6: Let (F_1, M) , (F_2, M) , (G_1, M) and (G_2, M) be soft sets over U . If $(F_1, M) \subseteq (G_1, M)$ and $(F_2, M) \subseteq (G_2, M)$ then $(F_1 \circ F_2, M) \subseteq (G_1 \circ G_2, M)$.

Proof: Let $x \in M$ can be expressible as $x = y\alpha z$ for $y, z \in M$, $\alpha \in \Gamma$. Then

$$(F_1 \circ F_2)(x) = \bigcap_{x=y\alpha z} \{F_1(y) \cup F_2(z)\}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\subseteq \bigcap_{x=y\alpha z} \{G_1(y) \cup G_2(z)\} \\ &= (G_1 \circ G_2)(x). \end{aligned}$$

Hence $(F_1 \circ F_2, M) \subseteq (G_1 \circ G_2, M)$.

If $x \in M$ cannot be expressible as $x = y\alpha z$ for $y, z \in M, \alpha \in \Gamma$. Then

$$(F_1 \circ F_2)(x) = U = (G_1 \circ G_2)(x).$$

Hence $(F_1 \circ F_2, M) \subseteq (G_1 \circ G_2, M)$.

Theorem 3.7: Let (F, M) be a soft set over U . Then (F, M) is a uni-soft Γ -semigroup over U if and only if $(F \circ F, M) \supseteq (F, M)$.

Proof: Let (F, M) be a uni-soft Γ -semigroup over U . Then for $x \in M$ with $x = y\alpha z, y, z \in M, \alpha \in \Gamma$, we have $F(x) = F(y\alpha z) \subseteq F(y) \cup F(z)$.

$$\begin{aligned} \therefore F(x) &\subseteq \bigcap_{x=y\alpha z} \{F(y) \cup F(z)\} \\ &= (F \circ F)(x) \text{ for } x \in M. \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore (F, M) \subseteq (F \circ F, M).$$

Conversely, Assume that $(F, M) \subseteq (F \circ F, M)$ and let $x, y \in M, \alpha \in \Gamma$. Then

$$F(x\alpha y) \subseteq (F \circ F)(x\alpha y).$$

$$\subseteq F(x) \cup F(y).$$

$$\therefore F(x\alpha y) \subseteq F(x) \cup F(y).$$

Hence (F, M) is a uni-soft Γ -semigroup over U .

Theorem 3.8: Let (K, M) be a soft set over U . Then for uni-empty soft set (χ_M, M) over U , (K, M) is a uni-soft left Γ -ideal over U if and only if $(K, M) \subseteq (\chi_M \circ K, M)$.

Proof: Let $(K, M) \subseteq (\chi_M \circ K, M)$ and $x, y \in M, \alpha \in \Gamma$. Then

$$K(x\alpha y) \subseteq (\chi_M \circ K)(x\alpha y) = \chi_M(x) \cup K(y) = \emptyset \cup K(y) = K(y).$$

$\therefore K(x\alpha y) \subseteq K(y)$. Hence (K, M) is a uni-soft left Γ -ideal over U .

Conversely, let (K, M) is a uni-soft left Γ -ideal of M over U and $y, z \in M, \alpha \in \Gamma$.

If $x = y\alpha z$, then

$$\begin{aligned} (\chi_M \circ K)(x) &= \bigcap_{x=y\alpha z} \{\chi_M(y) \cup K(z)\} \\ &\supseteq \bigcap_{x=y\alpha z} \{\emptyset \cup K(y\alpha z)\} \\ &= \bigcap_{x=y\alpha z} K(y\alpha z) \end{aligned}$$

$$= K(x).$$

Hence $(\chi_M \circ K, M) \supseteq (K, M)$.

Theorem 3.9: Let (K, M) be a soft set over U . Then for uni-empty soft set (χ_M, M) over U , (K, M) is a uni-soft right Γ -ideal over U if and only if $(K, M) \subseteq (K \circ \chi_M, M)$.

Proof: The proof of this theorem is analogous to the proof of theorem 6.1.15.

Corollary 3.10: Let (K, M) be a soft set over U . Then for uni-empty soft set (χ_M, M) over U , (K, M) is a uni-soft two sided Γ -ideal over U if and only if $(K, M) \subseteq (\chi_M \circ K, M)$ and $(K, M) \subseteq (K \circ \chi_M, M)$.

Theorem 3.11: The soft union of two uni-soft Γ -semigroups over a universal set is a uni-soft Γ -semigroup.

Proof: Let (F, M) and (G, M) be two uni-soft Γ -semigroup over U and $x, y \in M, \alpha \in \Gamma$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} (F \cup G)(x\alpha y) &= F(x\alpha y) \cup G(x\alpha y) \\ &\subseteq (F(x) \cup F(y)) \cup (G(x) \cup G(y)). \\ &= (F(x) \cup G(x)) \cup (F(y) \cup G(y)). \\ &= (F \cup G)(x) \cup (F \cup G)(y). \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore (F \cup G)(x\alpha y) \subseteq (F \cup G)(x) \cup (F \cup G)(y).$$

Hence $(F \cup G, M)$ is a uni-soft Γ -semigroup over U .

Theorem 3.12: The soft union of two uni-soft left Γ -ideals over a universal set is a uni-soft left Γ -ideal.

Proof: Let (F, M) and (G, M) be two uni-soft left Γ -ideals over U . Then for any $x, y \in M, \alpha \in \Gamma, F(x\alpha y) \subseteq F(y)$ and $G(x\alpha y) \subseteq G(y)$.

Consider, $(F \cup G)(x\alpha y) = F(x\alpha y) \cup G(x\alpha y)$

$$\begin{aligned} &\subseteq F(y) \cup G(y). \\ &= (F \cup G)(y). \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore (F \cup G)(x\alpha y) \subseteq (F \cup G)(y).$$

Hence $(F \cup G, M)$ is a uni-soft left Γ -ideal of M over U .

Similar result can be proved for two uni-soft right Γ -ideals of M over U and hence we have the following corollary.

Corollary 3.13: The soft union of two uni-soft two sided Γ -ideals over a universal set is a uni-soft two sided Γ -ideal of M over U .

Theorem 3.14: The uni-soft product of two uni-soft left Γ -ideals over a universal set is a uni-soft left Γ -ideal.

Proof: Let (F, M) and (G, M) be two uni-soft left Γ -ideals of M over U and $x, y \in M, \alpha \in \Gamma$.
 If $y = a\alpha b$ for some $a, b \in M, \alpha \in \Gamma$, then $x\beta y = x\beta(a\alpha b) = (x\beta a)\alpha b$.

$$\begin{aligned} \therefore ((F \circ G)(y)) &= \bigcap_{y=a\alpha b} \{F(a) \cup G(b)\} \\ &\supseteq \bigcap_{x\beta y=(x\beta a)\alpha b} \{F(x\beta a) \cup G(b)\} \\ &\supseteq \bigcap_{x\beta y=c\alpha b} \{F(c) \cup G(b)\}. \\ &= (F \circ G)(x\beta y). \end{aligned}$$

Hence $(F \circ G)(y) \supseteq (F \circ G)(x\beta y)$.

If $y \in M$ cannot be expressible as $y = a\alpha b$ for some $a, b \in M, \alpha \in \Gamma$, then

$(F \circ G)(y) = U \supseteq (F \circ G)(x\alpha y)$. $\therefore (F \circ G, M)$ is a uni-soft left Γ -ideal of M over U .

Similar result can be proved for two uni-soft right Γ -ideals of M over U and hence we have the following corollary.

Corollary 3.15: The uni-soft product of two uni-soft two sided Γ -ideals over a universal set is a uni-soft two sided Γ -ideal.

Theorem 3.16: Let (F, M) is a uni-soft Γ -semigroup over U . Then (F^*, M) is also a uni-soft Γ -semigroup over U .

Proof: Let $x, y \in M, \alpha \in \Gamma$. If $x, y \in e_M(F: \eta)$, then $x\alpha y \in e_M(F: \eta)$ as $e_M(F: \eta)$ is a Γ -sub-semigroup of M .

Hence $F^*(x\alpha y) = F(x\alpha y) \subseteq F(x) \cup F(y) = F^*(x) \cup F^*(y)$.

If $x \notin e_M(F: \eta)$ or $y \notin e_M(F: \eta)$, then $F^*(x) = \rho$ or $F^*(y) = \rho$.

Thus $F^*(x\alpha y) \subseteq \rho = \rho \cup \rho = F^*(x) \cup F^*(y)$.

$\therefore F^*(x\alpha y) \subseteq F^*(x) \cup F^*(y)$.

Hence (F^*, M) is a uni-soft Γ -semigroup over U .

Theorem 3.17: Let (F, M) is a uni-soft left (resp. right) Γ -ideal of M . Then (F^*, M) is also a uni-soft left (resp. right) Γ -ideal of M .

Corollary 3.18: Let (F, M) is a uni-soft two sided Γ -ideal of M . Then (F^*, M) is also a uni-soft two sided Γ -ideal of M .

Theorem 3.19: Let (F, M) and (G, M) be uni-soft right Γ -ideal and uni-soft left Γ -ideal of M respectively. Then $(F \circ G, M) \supseteq (F \cup G, M)$.

Proof: Let $x \in M$ be such that $x = a\alpha b$ for some $a, b \in M, \alpha \in \Gamma$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 (F \circ G)(x) &= \bigcap_{x=a\alpha b} \{ F(a) \cup G(b) \} \\
 &\supseteq \bigcap_{x=a\alpha b} F(a\alpha b) \cup G(a\alpha b) \\
 &= F(x) \cup G(x) \\
 &= (F \cup G)(x).
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore (F \circ G, M) \supseteq (F \cup G, M).$$

If $x \in M$ cannot be expressible as $x = a\alpha b$ for some $a, b \in M, \alpha \in \Gamma$. Then,

$$(F \circ G)(x) = U \supseteq (F \cup G)(x).$$

Hence $(F \circ G, M) \supseteq (F \cup G, M)$.

Theorem 3.20: Let M be a regular Γ -semigroup. If (F, M) is a uni-soft right Γ -ideal of M . Then $(F \cup G, M) \supseteq (F \circ G, M)$.

Proof: Let M be a regular Γ -semigroup. Then for $x \in M$ there exists $a \in M, \alpha, \beta \in \Gamma$ such that $x = x\alpha a\beta x$. Thus,

$$(F \circ G)(x) = \bigcap_{x=y\alpha z} \{ F(y) \cup G(z) \}$$

On the other hand, we have $(F \cup G)(x) = F(x) \cup G(x) \supseteq F(x\alpha a) \cup G(x)$.

Since $x = x\alpha a\beta x$, we obtain

$$F(x\alpha a) \cup G(x) \supseteq \bigcap_{x=y\alpha z} F(y) \cup G(z) = (F \circ G)(x)$$

$$\therefore (F \cup G)(x) \supseteq (F \circ G)(x).$$

$$\text{Hence } (F \cup G, M) \supseteq (F \circ G, M).$$

Similarly using the regularity condition in M we can prove $(F \cup G, M) \supseteq (F \circ G, M)$ when (G, M) is a uni-soft left Γ -ideal of M , for every soft set (F, M) over U .

Theorem 3.21: Let M be a regular Γ -semigroup. Then $(F \cup G, M) = (F \circ G, M)$ for every uni-soft right Γ -ideal (F, M) and uni-soft left Γ -ideal (G, M) of M .

Proof: From theorem 6.1.26 we have Then $(F \circ G, M) \supseteq (F \cup G, M)$ and from theorem 6.1.27 $(F \cup G, M) \supseteq (F \circ G, M)$.

$$\text{Hence } (F \cup G, M) = (F \circ G, M).$$

Remark 3.22: Every uni-soft left Γ -ideal of M over U is a uni-soft quasi Γ -ideal of M over U . For if, let us suppose that (F, M) be a uni-soft left Γ -ideal of M over U .

$$\text{Consider, } ((F \circ \chi_M) \cup (\chi_M \circ F))(x) = (F \circ \chi_M)(x) \cup (\chi_M \circ F)(x).$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \bigcap_{x=y\alpha z} \{F(y) \cup \chi_M(z)\} \cup \bigcap_{x=y\alpha z} \{\chi_M(y) \cup F(z)\} \\
 &= \bigcap_{x=y\alpha z} \{F(y) \cup \phi\} \cup \bigcap_{x=y\alpha z} \{\phi \cup F(z)\} \\
 &= \bigcap_{x=y\alpha z} F(y) \cup \bigcap_{x=y\alpha z} F(z) \\
 &\quad \supseteq \bigcap_{x=y\alpha z} F(y) \\
 &\quad \supseteq \bigcap_{x=y\alpha z} F(y\alpha z) \\
 &= F(x).
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus $((F \circ \chi_M) \cup (\chi_M \circ F))(x) \supseteq F(x)$.

Hence $(F, M) \subseteq (F \circ \chi_M, M) \cup (\chi_M \circ F, M)$.

\therefore Every uni-soft left Γ -ideal of M over U is a uni-soft quasi Γ -ideal of M over U .

Similarly we can show that every uni-soft right Γ -ideal of M over U is a uni-soft quasi Γ -ideal of M over U and hence have the result that every uni-soft two sided Γ -ideal of M over U is a uni-soft quasi Γ -ideal of M over U .

The converse of the above statement is not true. i.e., every uni-soft quasi Γ -ideal of M over U need not be a uni-soft left Γ -ideal or uni-soft right Γ -ideal of M over U .

Theorem 3.23: Let Q be a non-empty subset of M . Then Q is a quasi Γ -ideal of M if and only if the uni-characteristic soft set (χ_Q, M) is a uni-soft quasi- Γ -ideal of M over U .

Proof: Let Q be a quasi Γ -ideal of M and $a \in M$ be such that $a \in Q$. Then,

$$\chi_Q(a) = \emptyset \subseteq ((\chi_Q \circ \chi_M) \cup (\chi_M \circ \chi_Q))(a).$$

If $a \notin Q$, then $\chi_Q(a) = U$. Assume that $((\chi_Q \circ \chi_M) \cup (\chi_M \circ \chi_Q))(a) = \emptyset$. Then $(\chi_Q \circ \chi_M)(a) = \emptyset$ and $(\chi_M \circ \chi_Q)(a) = \emptyset$. Hence,

$$\bigcap_{a=b\alpha c} \{\chi_Q(b) \circ \chi_M(c)\} = \emptyset$$

And

$$\bigcap_{a=d\alpha e} \{\chi_M(d) \circ \chi_Q(e)\} = \emptyset$$

This shows that $\chi_Q(b) = \emptyset$ and $\chi_Q(e) = \emptyset$ with $a = b\alpha c$ and $a = d\alpha e$ for b, c, d and $e \in M, \alpha \in \Gamma$. Hence $b, e \in Q$.

Thus, for $b \in Q, \alpha \in \Gamma$ and $c \in M$, $bac \in Q\Gamma M$ and for $d \in M, \alpha \in \Gamma$ and $e \in Q$, $dae \in M\Gamma Q$. Hence $a = bac = dae \in Q\Gamma M \cap M\Gamma Q \subseteq Q$. which shows that $a \in Q$. This contradicts the fact that $a \notin Q$. Hence $\chi_Q(a) \subseteq ((\chi_Q \circ \chi_M) \cup (\chi_M \circ \chi_Q))(a)$.

$$\therefore (\chi_Q, M) \subseteq (\chi_Q \circ \chi_M, M) \cup (\chi_M \circ \chi_Q, M)$$

$\therefore (\chi_Q, M)$ is a uni-soft quasi Γ -ideal of M over U .

Conversely, suppose that (χ_Q, M) is a uni-soft quasi Γ -ideal of M over U . Let $a \in Q\Gamma M \cap M\Gamma Q$. Then $a = b\alpha x$ for some $b \in Q, \alpha \in \Gamma, x \in M$ and also $a = y\alpha c$ for some $y \in M, \alpha \in \Gamma, c \in Q$. Since (χ_Q, M) is a uni-soft quasi Γ -ideal of M over U , $(\chi_Q, M) \subseteq (\chi_Q \circ \chi_M, M) \cup (\chi_M \circ \chi_Q, M)$.

$$\text{Thus } \chi_Q(a) \subseteq ((\chi_Q \circ \chi_M) \cup (\chi_M \circ \chi_Q))(a).$$

$$= (\chi_Q \circ \chi_M)(a) \cup (\chi_M \circ \chi_Q)(a).$$

$$= \bigcap_{a=b\alpha x} \{\chi_Q(b) \cup \chi_M(x)\} \cup \bigcap_{a=y\alpha c} \{\chi_M(y) \cup \chi_Q(c)\}$$

$$= \bigcap_{a=b\alpha x} \{\chi_Q(b) \cup \emptyset\} \cup \bigcap_{a=y\alpha c} \{\emptyset \cup \chi_Q(c)\}$$

$$= \bigcap_{a=b\alpha x} \chi_Q(b) \cup \bigcap_{a=y\alpha c} \chi_Q(c)$$

$$= \emptyset \cup \emptyset = \emptyset.$$

$$\chi_Q(a) = \emptyset.$$

Hence $a \in Q$.

$$\therefore Q\Gamma M \cap M\Gamma Q \subseteq Q.$$

$\therefore Q$ is a quasi Γ -ideal of M .

4. Reference

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